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Correction: A study on the dependence of bacteria adhesion on the polymer nanofibre diameter

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Correction for 'A study on the dependence of bacteria adhesion on the polymer nanofibre diameter' by Fabrizio De Cesare *et al.*, *Environ. Sci.: Nano*, 2019, 6, 778–797.

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There were errors in Table 1 in the original article. The reference numbers in the last column in Table 1 were incorrect. The correct reference numbers are shown in the Table below. Please refer to the original article for the corresponding reference details. Also, the entries in rows 14–17 of the “Topography motifs” column, in rows 3–5 and 14 of the “Topography material” column, in rows 5 and 7–13 of the “Topography dimensions” column, and in rows 5 and 10–13 of the “BFR or BFR_{like}” column in Table 1 were incorrect. The correct entries are shown in the Table below.

Table 1 Bacteria adhesion as related to substrate topography: interactions between bacteria species and fibrous and fibrous-like topography motifs expressed through the bacteria-to-fibre or bacteria-to-fibre-like ratio (BFR or BFR_{like}) (see the text [in the main article] for more details) obtained from some publications (Ref. column)

Bacteria	Topography motifs	Topography material	Topography dimensions ^a	Bacteria dimensions	BFR or BFR _{like}	Notes	Ref.
<i>Burkholderia terricola</i>	Fibres	Polycaprolactone	20–180 nm diameter (coated fibres), 10–129 nm diameter (pristine fibres)	0.5 µm diam., 1.5 µm length	50–3.88 diameter (measured in pristine fibres), 22.7–1.67 (measured in coated fibres), 25–2.78 (measured in bacteria-binding fibres)	Always BFR > 1. Prevalent colonisation when cells aligned along 99 nm wide nanofibres in a train-like shape, before forming clusters and then microcolonies	This work
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	Fibres	Polystyrene	300–3000 nm diameter	0.5 µm diam., 2 µm length	1.7–0.17	Prevalent colonisation, when BFR = 1. BFR < 1: cells aligned along single fibres in a train-like shape, BFR ≤ 1: cells maintained the original rod-like shape and formed clusters in the fibrous weave, BFR > 1 cells distorted and wrapped around the fibres	32
<i>Serratia proteamaculans</i>	Fibres	Cellulose acetate	500–3000 nm diameter	0.5 µm diam., 2 µm length	1–0.17	Prevalent colonisation in the fibrous weave	29
<i>Achromobacter xylosoxidans</i>	Fibres	Cellulose acetate	500–3000 nm diameter	0.5 µm diam., 1.5 µm length	1–0.17	Prevalent colonisation in the fibrous weave	29
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	Fibres	Polystyrene	70–1100 nm diameter	0.5 µm diam., 1.8 µm length	7.1–0.45	Prevalent colonisation in the interfibre spacing, BFR < 1: greater cell accumulation. BFR > 1: lower colonisation. BFR = 1: intermediate adhesion	12

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Table 1 (continued)

Bacteria	Topography motifs	Topography material	Topography dimensions ^a	Bacteria dimensions	BFR or BFR _{like}	Notes	Ref.
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	Fibres	Cellulose	1080–16 500 nm diameter	0.5 μm diam., 2 μm length	0.46–0.03	Prevalent colonisation in the interfibre spacing; BFR < 1	31
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	Fibres	PCL	800–6430 nm diameter	0.5 μm diam., 1.5 μm length	0.63–0.08	Distribution on the fibres with random orientation; BFR < 1	34
<i>Acinetobacter baumannii</i>	Fibres	PCL	800–6430 nm diameter	0.5 μm diam., 0.8 μm length	0.63–0.08	A single cell visibly oriented longitudinally; BFR < 1	34
<i>Listeria monocytogenes</i>	Fibres	PCL	800–6430 nm diameter	0.5 μm diam., 1.2 μm length	0.63–0.08	No clear image supporting orientation and distribution	34
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	Fibres	PCL	800–6430 nm diameter	0.5 μm diam., 2 μm length	0.63–0.08	Distribution on the fibres with random orientation; BFR < 1	35
<i>Pseudomonas putida</i>	Fibres	PCL	800–6430 nm diameter	0.55 μm diam., 1.55 μm length	0.69–0.09	Distribution on the fibres with random orientation; BFR < 1	35
<i>Brevundimonas diminuta</i>	Fibres	PCL	800–6430 nm diameter	0.31 μm diam., 0.68 μm length	0.39–0.05	Distribution on the fibres with random orientation; BFR < 1	35
<i>Sphingobium fuliginis</i>	Fibres	PCL	800–6430 nm diameter	0.5 μm diam., 2.0 μm length	0.63–0.08	Distribution on the fibres with random orientation; BFR < 1	35
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	Posts	Epoxy	300 nm diameter; 2 μm height	0.5 μm diam., 1.5 μm length	1.7 ^b	Adhesion to posts depends on spacing: the closer to bacteria dimensions, the greater the adhesion	82
<i>Shewanella oneidensis</i>	Wires	Si	300 nm diameter, 3 μm height	0.6 μm diameter; 2.5 μm length	2 ^b	Bacteria preferred to stay on the nanowires rather than travel through the planar substrate, expressing a distinct interaction with the nanowires	83
<i>Sporomusa ovata</i>	Wires	Si	800 nm diameter; 25–30 μm height	0.5 μm diameter; 5 μm length	0.6 ^b	Bacteria preferentially grew aligned with the nanowires especially with increasing ionic concentrations	84
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	Pillars	Si	1300 nm diameter; 3.2 μm height	1.0 μm diameter; 2 μm length	0.8 ^b	Bacteria growing on both the pillars (aligned) and in pitches (preferentially)	81

^a Dimensions of the pristine materials, *i.e.* ignoring the possible variations due to the presence of coating conditioning films. ^b BFR_{like} values.

The Royal Society of Chemistry apologises for these errors and any consequent inconvenience to authors and readers.

